

Identification of new studies via EMBASE, MEDLINE, and bioRxiv

Identification

Records identified from:
EMBASE (N = 3,772)
MEDLINE (N = 3,638)
bioRxiv (N = 966)

Records removed before screening:
Duplicate records (N = 1,793)

Records screened (N = 6,583)

Records removed after title and abstract
screened (N = 6,306)

Articles sought for retrieval (N = 277)

Articles not retrieved (conference abstract,
no response from author, or data not
available N = 25)

Articles assessed for eligibility (N = 252)

Articles excluded:
Conference abstract with article included in
search (N = 23)
Duplicate (N = 23)
Adiposity not the exposure (N = 15)
Commentary (N = 8)
Not MR (N = 4)
Erratum (N = 3)
Preprint in which published paper did not
include MR (N = 1)
Conference proceedings (N = 1)
Not in English (N = 1)

Total articles included in review (N = 173)

Articles included in meta-analyses included
more than one MR analysis (study). Studies
were excluded from meta-analyses if they
were the only study to investigate an
exposure-outcome association, or if there
was population overlap between one studies
outcome and another studies outcome, or if
there was overlap with one studies exposure
and another studies outcome. In these
instances, the study with the larger sample
size was retained. In addition, studies
investigating the effect of adjusted variables
in two-sample settings were excluded given
recent evidence of biased estimates when
using adjusted traits.

Total meta-analysed articles (N = 34)
Total meta-analysed studies (N = 66)
Total meta-analyses (N = 29)

Included